

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

PLANTS AS AN INTERESTING OBJECT FOR SCIENCE AND PRODUCTION

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Abstract

This article examines plants as important objects of scientific research and practical production. The study highlights the ecological, biological, agricultural, and economic significance of plants, emphasizing their essential role in oxygen production, food chains, climate regulation, and sustainable development. Special attention is given to the importance of plants in biotechnology, genetics, ecosystem stability, and environmental protection. The article also discusses the relevance of plant studies in addressing global ecological challenges, biodiversity conservation, and the impact of invasive species. It is concluded that comprehensive plant research remains highly important for modern science and society.

Keywords: plants, biodiversity, sustainable development, ecology, plant science.

As is known, all living things are constantly in food and energy exchange with the environment in order to continue their life activities and participate in the ecological functions they perform in nature, and this is characteristic of both producers (plants), consumers (animals), and reducers (fungi and bacteria) in an ecological sense. However, the dependence of consumers, as well as reducers, on the environment is a more sensitive feature than that of producers, since both of the latter, namely fungi and animals, are heterotrophic in terms of nutrition [158], that is, since they cannot carry out the photosynthesis process, their need for organic matter, as well as oxygen, is met by other sources, primarily plants. Since plants play an important role in providing food for most living things, their comprehensive study has always been relevant and continues to maintain this status in full force today. This allows us to state this in the following general terms as a result of the analysis of the literature data:

People's ideas about plants are based on a wide spectrum of their activities and cover, or rather touch, all areas of human life. Because from the moment human civilization arose and began to develop, it has depended on the management of plants, and in a number of cases this issue failed due to the lack of necessary knowledge. Nevertheless, throughout history, plants have been collected, become objects of trade, selectively adapted to new habitats and propagated in order to obtain individuals with new characteristics. As a logical consequence of this, plants have been manipulated for various (food, feed, medical, technical, etc.) purposes, including aesthetic (decorative properties), and this situation continues to this day. Moreover, modern civilization is based on the more efficient and sustainable use of the biological and physical resources of plants in accordance with the principles of sustainable development. Because even today, our understanding of the environment is still incomplete and there are many issues that need to be clarified, which cannot be solved without a comprehensive study of plants. The importance of this situation is more pronounced in the current global

problems in the world, as well as in the modern level of development of science and technology.

It is known that most living things on Earth cannot live without atmospheric air, that is, oxygen, that is, they are aerobic. The role of plants, as well as some microorganisms, is indispensable in meeting the needs of living things in this regard. Thus, only plants and some microorganisms meet the needs of living things for oxygen and organic matter by converting solar energy into chemical energy. Their role does not end there, and the mentioned group of living things plays an important role in regulating the chemical and biological state of the climate, soil and water, is the source of minerals (for example, coal) that we are depleting today, that is, it is an easily accessible renewable energy source for the future. In addition, the irreplaceable role of plants, as well as photosynthetic bacteria, in regulating the substances occurring in the biosphere, primarily the carbon cycle, in making atmospheric nitrogen, which is in a symbiotic relationship with microorganisms and inert, usable by all living things, in preventing soil erosion and water pollution, in improving the ecological aspects of open and closed environments where people operate, etc. is a reality that no one doubts today. It is no coincidence that in modern times, plants are considered to be one of the integral components of the "One Health" strategy. Nevertheless, the negative consequences of human industrial activity, namely the increasing burden of anthropogenic impact on the environment, the increasing number of world population against the background of these events, and other consequences of the use of nature, can change the buffer system of natural processes regulating the global climate to such an extent that the global climate change that humanity is already experiencing today can be an example of this. The further development of the Earth also depends on the results that people will achieve in a more intelligent and efficient use of plant life. It should be noted that plants differ from other living things in a number of qualities, which is the basis of scientific and practical interest in them. It would be logical to substantiate this idea by touching on some of these differences.

Firstly, only a few phytohormones are required for the transformation of undifferentiated, i.e. somatic cells of plants into mature individuals, and it is possible to regenerate an entire organism from cells of vegetative (leaf and root) organs. An analogous feature is not found in animals.

Secondly, as mentioned, plants are practically the main and only source of organic substances on Earth, primarily oxygen. This is due to the presence of chloroplasts capable of collecting solar energy in plants, the synthesis of 20 essential amino acids necessary for the formation of proteins, including 9 that are not produced by humans (valine, tryptophan and phenylalanine, leucine, isoleucine, lysine, methionine and threonine), and the ability to fix nitrogen in the atmosphere, which living things in the atmosphere, as well as plants themselves, cannot use.

Thirdly, despite the fact that plants do not have the main organ system, that is, the nervous system, which is found in animals, their physiological properties are that they react to what is happening in the environment. In addition to the immune system, plants have an induction mechanism that provides resistance to diseases caused by pathogens and the toxins they synthesize.

Fourthly, primitive and higher plants form the initial link in the food chain in terrestrial and aquatic systems. For this reason, plants occupy a central place in agriculture, and together with microorganisms and domestic animals, they can play the role of a source of raw materials for human nutrition, for people for various purposes, for example, clothing, construction materials, etc. In addition, the application of basic information about plants, for example, the study of plant nutrient requirements allows for the management of soil fertility, and allows us to confidently state that plants still have the potential to solve existing problems in the modern era, and therefore their research in various aspects is still relevant today.

Fifth, although the science of ecology has made great progress in terms of understanding the dynamics of ecosystems and the processes that regulate their trophic structure, systematic differences between ecosystems still remain [256], which leads to the fact that controversial issues still remain. The elimination of these can only be achieved through a comprehensive study of the plants in the ecosystem. By the way, there are no studies in the Republic of Azerbaijan aimed at studying biodiversity at the ecosystem level.

In addition to the above, as a result of the study of plants, a number of issues that have played an important role in the development of modern biology and are still based on it, such as Mendel's laws that form the basis of genetics (experiments conducted on peas), the phytochrome phenomenon, the transposition of genetic elements (maize), the protein nature of enzymes, etc. has been clarified, that is, plants are also used as model organisms, which allows us to confidently state once again that plants are interesting and relevant objects of

research of any aspect and that it is necessary to conduct research in these directions.

In addition, the study of plants is also related to another point, which is related to the occurrence of invasions. Thus, as a result of a number of studies conducted, it becomes clear that thousands of local species have disappeared due to invasive, that is, introduced species [185]. Preventing this is important both in terms of the Rio de Janeiro Convention on Biodiversity and in terms of solving the problems arising from globalization. This issue, namely the study of plants in the conditions of Azerbaijan, is also important from another point, since the fact that a certain part of its territory has been under occupation for 30 years, the ecological terror carried out by the occupiers, as well as the fact that most of the water used for irrigation of agricultural crops is carried out at the expense of transboundary rivers, also allows us to confidently state this.

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